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**Studies on Thiadiazole Derivatives. Part-III.
Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of
p,p'-Bis(2-substituted-benzalmino/benzoyl-
amino/sulphonamido-1,3,4-thiadiazol-5-
ylmethylamino)diphenyl Sulphones**

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DAPSONE is a useful chemotherapeutic agent¹. In view of the wide spectrum of activity associated with thiadiazole derivatives², it was planned to synthesise thiadiazole derivatives bearing dapsone moiety. *p,p'*-Bis(2-substituted-benzal / benzoyl / sulphonamido - 1, 3, 4 - thiadiazol - 5 - ylmethylamino) - diphenyl sulphones were synthesised by the condensation of different aromatic aldehydes, acid chlorides and sulphonyl chlorides with *p,p'*-bis(2-amino-1,3,4-thiadiazol-5-yl-methylamino)diphenyl sulphone. The latter was prepared by the condensation of thiosemicarbazide with *p,p'*-bis(carboxymethylamino)diphenyl sulphone in presence of phosphorous oxychloride. Chloroacetic acid was condensed with *p,p'*-diamino diphenyl sulphone in presence of alkaline medium to get *p,p'*-bis(carboxymethylamino)diphenyl sulphone.

The structural assignments of the products were based on their elemental analyses, ir, nmr and mass spectral data. The products were screened for their antimicrobial activity.

Antimicrobial activity: The antimicrobial screening of thiadiazole derivatives was carried out using cup-plate method³ at a concentration of 50 µg using gram-positive bacteria *B. mega* and *B. saphilis*, gram-negative bacteria *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas fluores* and fungus *Aspergillus niger*.

Most of the compounds were found moderately active against different strain of bacteria and fungi (10–20 mm zone of inhibition). The maximum activity was observed in compounds bearing 3-aminophenyl, 3-hydroxy, 4-carboxyphenyl and 3-chlorophenyl groups against *B. saphilis*, and 4-acetamidophenyl and 3-nitrophenyl groups against *B. mega*.

Experimental

Melting points of the compounds were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu DR-1 435-IR spectrophotometer.

p,p'-Bis(carboxymethylamino)diphenyl sulphone : *p,p'*-Bis(diaminodiphenyl sulphone (0.01 mol, 2.48 g) and monochloroacetic acid (0.02 mol, 1.89 g) was condensed at 110° in presence of 15% NaOH solution for 12 h. The contents were poured into ice-water and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, (2.44 g, 67%), m.p. 102° (Found : C, 57.89; H, 4.79; N, 11.20. C₁₆H₁₆N₂O₆S requires : C, 58.04; H, 4.87; N, 11.28%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1 145, 1 290 cm⁻¹ (S=O asym, sym), 1 680 cm⁻¹ (C=O), 3 300 (NH), and 3 450 cm⁻¹ (OH).

p,p'-Bis(2-amino-1,3,4-thiadiazol-5-yl-methylamino)diphenyl sulphone⁴ : A mixture of *p,p'*-bis(carboxymethylamino)diphenyl sulphone (3.64 g, 0.01 mol), thiosemicarbazide (1.82 g, 0.02 mol) and phosphorous oxychloride (1.87 g, 0.02 mol) was heated at 60° for 1 h and then at 90–95° for 1.5 h.

The contents were poured into cool alkaline water at 10° and the resulting solid was crystallised from dioxane-DMF (3 : 1) solvent, (3.03 g, 64%), m.p. 98° (Found: C, 45.52; H, 3.80; N, 7.13. C₁₈H₁₈N₈O₂S₃ requires: C, 45.55; H, 3.82; N, 7.19%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 400, 3 275 (NH asym, sym), 1 310 (C-N), 1 660 (C=N), 605 (C-S-C), 1 030 cm⁻¹ (N-N thiadiazol moiety), 1 145 and 1 295 cm⁻¹ (S=O, asym, sym).

p,p'-Bis(2-substituted-benzalamino-1,3,4-thiadiazol-5-yl-methylamino)diphenyl sulphone (1): A mixture of benzaldehyde (2.1 ml, 0.02 mol), *p,p'*-bis(2-amino-1,3,4-thiadiazol-5-ylmethylamino)diphenyl sulphone (4.75 g, 0.01 mol) and acetic acid (5-6 drops) was refluxed in ethanol on a water-bath for 6 h. The reaction mixture was then poured into crushed ice and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol-dioxane (3 : 1) solvent, (3.75 g, 64%), m.p. 180° (Found: C, 65.37; H, 4.45; N, 19.06. C₃₂H₂₆N₈O₂S requires: C, 61.51; H, 4.46; N, 19.10%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 1 630 (N=CH), 1 690-1 630 (C=N), 605 (C-S-C), 1 030 (N-N thiadiazol moiety), 1 145 and 1 295 cm⁻¹ (S=O asym, sym); δ (DMSO-d₆) 5.2 (4H, s, NH-CH₂), 7.1 (2H, s, CH=N) and 6.5-7.6 (16H, d, ArH).

Similarly, other compounds (1) were prepared (Table 1).

p,p'-Bis(2-substituted-benzalamino-1,3,4-thiadiazol-5-yl-methylamino)diphenyl sulphones (2): A mixture of benzoic acid (2.44 g, 0.02 mol) and thionyl chloride (2.5 ml) in chloroform (40 ml) was refluxed for 6 h. Excess of thionyl chloride was then removed under reduced pressure and the acid chloride was refluxed with *p,p'*-bis(2-amino-1,3,4-thiadiazol-5-ylmethylamino)diphenyl sulphone (4.76 g, 0.01 mol) in chloroform (20 ml) and 2 to 3 drops of pyridine for further 2 h. The resulting solid was crystallised from methanol-dioxane (3 : 1) solvent, (4.91 g, 71%), m.p. 176° (Found: C, 55.35; H, 5.22; N, 16.14. C₃₂H₂₆N₈O₄S₃ requires: C, 55.46; H, 5.23; N, 16.17%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 1 660 (C=O), 1 520 (NH def, str), 1 315 (NH def, C-N str amide moiety), 1 695 (C=N), 605 (C-S-C), 1 030 (N-N thiadiazol moiety), 1 295 and 1 145 cm⁻¹ (S=O, sym, asym); δ (DMSO-d₆) 5.2 (4H, s, NH-CH₂), 8.15 (2H, s, NH-CH₂), 8.5 (2H, s, NH-SO₂) and 6.8-7.8 (16H, d, ArH).

Similarly, other compounds (2) were prepared (Table 1).

p,p'-Bis(2-arylsulphonamido-1,3,4-thiadiazol-5-yl-methylamino)diphenyl sulphones (3): A mixture of benzoylsulphonyl chloride (2.56 ml, 0.02 mol), *p,p'*-bis(2-amino-1,3,4-thiadiazol-5-yl-methylamino)-diphenyl sulphone (4.74 g, 0.01 mol) and pyridine (5 ml) was refluxed for 3 h. The contents were then poured into cold water and the resulting solid was washed with dilute hydrochloric acid and crystallised from methanol-dioxane (3 : 1) mixture, (4.69 g, 68%), m.p. 170° (Found: C, 52.09; H, 3.72; N, 16.20. C₃₀H₂₆N₈O₆S₃ requires: C, 52.16; H, 3.74; N, 16.22%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 1 360 (S=O sym), 1 170 (S=O asym), 3 400 (NH), 1 360 (C-N str,

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Compd. no.	R	M p °C	Yield
1a	Phenyl	180	54
1b	4-Tolyl	174	63
1c	2-Chlorophenyl	165	68
1d	4-Chlorophenyl	169	60
1e	7,6-Dichlorophenyl	194	69
1f	3-Aminophenyl	164	70
1g	4-Aminophenyl	168	68
1h	2-Hydroxyphenyl	159	64
1i	4-Hydroxyphenyl	164	66
1j	2-Methoxyphenyl	174	68
1k	4-Methoxyphenyl	178	64
1l	3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl	203	62
1m	3-Methoxy-4-hydroxyphenyl	201	62
1n	3-Nitrophenyl	176	63
1o	Cinnamyl	148	64
1p	4-Dimethylaminophenyl	154	66
2a	Phenyl	170	68
2b	4-Tolyl	178	70
2c	4-Chlorophenyl	186	74
2d	4-Bromophenyl	182	66
2e	4-Iodophenyl	169	69
2f	4-Acetamidophenyl	139	62
2g	3-Hydroxy-4-carboxyphenyl	165	62
2h	2,5-Dichlorophenyl	164	64
2i	2-Naphthyl	125	70
3a	Phenyl	176	71
3b	2-Methylphenyl	166	69
3c	4-Methylphenyl	160	65
3d	2-Chlorophenyl	172	70
3e	3-Chlorophenyl	174	74
3f	3-Hydroxyphenyl	149	58
3g	4-Hydroxyphenyl	144	57
3h	2,4-Dihydroxyphenyl	165	56
3i	2,6-Dihydroxyphenyl	175	55
3j	1-Hydroxy-2-naphthyl	170	64
3k	2-Hydroxy-3-naphthyl	134	70
3l	2-Methoxyphenyl	164	64
3m	4-Methoxyphenyl	170	68
3n	3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl	174	74
3o	2-Nitrophenyl	158	74
3p	3-Nitrophenyl	154	79
3q	3-Pyridyl	205	54
3r	4-Pyridyl	208	62
3s	4-Bromophenyl	195	70

*All compounds gave satisfactory N analysis.

sulphonamide moiety), 1 690 (C=N), 605 (C-S-C), 1 030 (N-N, thiadiazol moiety), 1 295 and 1 145 cm⁻¹ (S=O sym, asym); δ (DMSO-d₆) 5.2 (4H, s, NH-CH₂), 8.3 (2H, s, NH-CH₂), 8.6 (2H, s, NHCO) and 7.1-7.8 (16H, d, ArH).

Similarly, other compounds (3) were prepared (Table 1).

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- 3a; Ar=4-ClC₆H₄ g; Ar=4-NCC₆H₄
 b; Ar=4-Me₂NC₆H₄ h; Ar=4-BrC₆H₄
 c; Ar=2-O₂NC₆H₄ i; Ar=4-CH₂CH₂C₆H₄
 d; Ar=3,4,5-(MeO)₃C₆H₂ j; Ar=4-OH-3-OCH₃C₆H₃
 e; Ar=3,4-Cl₂C₆H₃ k; Ar=3,4-(HO)₂C₆H₃
 f; Ar=4-i.PrC₆H₄ l; Ar=2-Br-C₆H₄

Synthesis and Antibacterial Activity of 5-Arylidene-1,2,4-triazino[4,3-*b*]-1,2-benzisothiazol-3-one-6,6-dioxides

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TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3a-1*

Compd. no.	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula
3a	201	65	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ ClN ₃ O ₅ S
b	254	68	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₅ S
c	150	68	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₅ S
d	186	64	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₅ S
e	120	69	C ₁₈ H ₉ Cl ₂ N ₃ O ₅ S
f	182	61	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₅ S
g	>250	62	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₅ S
h	180	65	C ₁₈ H ₁₀ BrN ₃ O ₅ S
i	145	61	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₅ S
j	132	63	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₅ S
k	200	62	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₅ S
l	198	62	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ BrN ₃ O ₅ S

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analysis.

HETEROCYCLES containing nitrogen and sulphur, especially derivatives of 1,2-benzisothiazole-1,1-dioxides¹ and 1,2,4-triazines² are known to exhibit biological activity. With this in view an attempt has been made to incorporate both the moieties in a single class of compounds, viz. 1,2,4-triazino[4,3-*b*]-1,2-benzisothiazol-3-one-6,6-dioxide (2) and its various arylidene derivatives (3) and to study the antibacterial activity of the latter. Compound 2 was prepared by heating 2-ethoxycarbonylmethyl-3-hydrazino-1,2-benzisothiazole-1,1-dioxide³ (1) in benzene using *p*-toluene sulphonic acid (*p*-TSA) as a catalyst. This was condensed with various substituted benzaldehydes (3a-1).

Biological screening: Compounds 3a-1 (40 mg each) were evaluated for their antibacterial activity on gram positive bacterium *Staphylococcus aureus* and gram negative bacteria *Salmonella typhosa*, *Shigella dysenteriae*, *Pseudomonas pyocyanse* and *Proteus vulgaris* using Ditch-plate method⁴.

The compounds (Table 1) showed no activity against *P. vulgaris*, *P. pyocyanse* and *S. dysenteriae* (except 3k, to which this organism is sensitive). *S. aureus* was sensitive to all the compounds and *S. typhosa* was sensitive to all but four compounds, viz. 3a, b, k and l.

Experimental

Melting points were determined by open capillary method and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 681 spectrophotometer, pmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Hitachi R-600 spectrometer using TMS as internal standard and mass spectra on a Shimadzu QP-1000 spectrometer. Homogeneity of the compounds was checked by tlc.

Preparation of 2: A suspension of 1 (2.83 g, 0.01 mol) in benzene (40 ml) containing a few crystals of *p*-TSA was refluxed for 6 h using a Dean-Stark apparatus. After removal of the calculated amount of water, the heating was discontinued, the solution cooled to room temperature and benzene was distilled off under reduced pressure. The resulting white solid after cooling, was washed with hexane, (1.85 g, 78%), m.p. 135° (Found: C, 45.52; H, 3.02; N, 18.00. C₉H₇N₃O₅S requires: C, 45.56; H, 2.95; N, 17.72%); ν_{max} 1 650 (CONH) and 3 380 br cm⁻¹ (NH); δ 3.4 (2H, s, CH₂) and 7.5-8.0 (4H, m, ArH).

General method for the synthesis of 3a-1: A mixture of 2 (0.0042 mol), the corresponding benzaldehyde (0.005 mol) in benzene (35 ml) and the catalyst *p*-TSA was refluxed for 5 h using Dean-